

FAIR-IMPACT

Expanding FAIR solutions across EOSC

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1 M5.7 - Pilot for FAIR data object and code assessment in a disciplinary context

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Description
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
EC	European Commission

4 Introduction

This milestone draws together the pilot study efforts around FAIR assessment of discipline-specific metrics for data and research software, undertaken at the same time and in the context of two previous milestones, “M5.4 - Practical tests for automated FAIR digital object assessment in disciplinary context”¹ and “M5.6 - Practical tests for automated FAIR software assessment in a disciplinary context”². The specific disciplinary use case context linked to this work package was the social sciences, represented by the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA)³ through consortium partners UESSEX-UKDS and KNAW-DANS who are also CESSDA Service Providers (CESSDA SP).

¹ Huber, R., Mihai, H., & Verburg, M. (2023). M5.4 Practical tests for automated FAIR digital object assessment in disciplinary context (V1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10402148>

² Moraw, K., Antonioletti, M., Breitmoser, E., Chue Hong, N., & Priddy, M. (2024). M5.6 - Practical tests for automated FAIR software assessment in a disciplinary context (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10890043>

³ <https://www.cessda.eu/>

5 Description of the Milestone

Deliverable “D5.1 - Implementing metrics for automated FAIR digital objects assessment in a disciplinary context”⁴ defined a set of 17 metrics and tests (section “2.2 Draft FAIR metrics for the social sciences”) based upon the FAIRsFAIR project⁵ 17 minimum viable metrics⁶, analysis of FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs)⁷ from the social science community and CESSDA SPs, of which only 5 are specific to CESSDA and the social science community.

Milestone “M5.4 - Practical tests for automated FAIR digital object assessment in disciplinary context” (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10402148>) details the technical integration of the new metrics into the F-UJI tool (version 3.0.0), made available as open source, and the implementation of the 6 practical tests were assessed through the running of automated FAIR assessments against the list of data objects in milestone “M5.1 - Reference collection of test data sets”⁸ which is also presented in milestone M5.4 (section “4.2 Assessment results for the reference collection datasets”). The results of the assessment of the reference collection were the product of the merging of the social science metric implementation in F-UJI, as these only covers those metrics which differ from the domain-agnostic metrics, with those domain-agnostic results not covered by the discipline specific subset already collected during the domain agnostic tests, to enable a comparison of results. Although this successfully replicates a F-UJI automated FAIR assessment and facilitates comparability it is not one that can be used by others, either from a CESSDA SP or a potential reuser of a dataset.

In milestone M5.4 it was noted that the F-UJI FAIRness scores were significantly lower when using the discipline-specific metrics for social sciences. Possible reasons for this were suggested, such as strictness of standards required, however further investigations are warranted to determine if the low scores are factor of the metadata associated with the dataset, or an issue with the pass-fail tests which contribute, for example with testing the OAI-PMH endpoints (section “4.2 Assessment results for the reference collection datasets”), or if the metrics are too restrictive for the broader social science community beyond CESSDA.

Deliverable “D5.2 - Metrics for automated FAIR software assessment in a disciplinary context”⁹ describes 17 metrics that can be used to automate the assessment of research

⁴ Robert Huber, Maaïke Verburg, Mike Priddy, Hervé L'Hours, Joy Davidson, & Hannah Mihai. (2023). D5.1 Implementing metrics for automated FAIR digital objects assessment in a disciplinary context (V1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7784120>

⁵ FAIRsFAIR: Fostering FAIR Data Practices in Europe <https://fairsfair.eu/>

⁶ Devaraju, Anusuriya; Huber, Robert, Mokrane, Mustapha, Herterich, Patricia, Cepinskas, Linas, de Vries, Jerry, L'Hours, Herve, Davidson, Joy, & Angus White. (2022). FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics (0.5). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3775793>

⁷ <https://www.go-fair.org/how-to-go-fair/fair-implementation-profile/>

⁸ Robert Huber, & Maaïke Verburg. (2023). M5.1 - Reference collection of test data sets (v1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7746205>

⁹ Chue Hong, N., Breitmoser, E., Antonioletti, M., Davidson, J., Garijo, D., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Gruenpeter, M., Huber, R., Jonquet, C., priddy, M., Shepherdson, J., Verburg, M., & Wood, C. (2023). D5.2 - Metrics for automated FAIR software assessment in a disciplinary context (1.0 - DRAFT not yet approved by the European Commission). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10047401>

software against the FAIR Principles for Research Software (FAIR4RS Principles)¹⁰. The extent to which a principle has been satisfied by a research software object can be measured against the criteria in a metric via a set of tests.

The initial work in defining and implementing the research software metric tests in the F-UJI tool can be found in the milestone “M5.6 - Practical tests for automated FAIR software assessment in a disciplinary context” (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10890043>). There are a number of metrics and tests in the discipline-agnostic F-UJI FAIR data assessment which can also be utilised for FAIR research software assessment, thus milestone M5.6 concentrated on those metrics which were not common such as the full implementation of two of these metrics, FRSM-13¹¹ (dependencies, build and configuration) and FRSM-15¹² (licensing information), as well as providing skeletons for other research software specific metrics.

Additionally, discipline-specific versions of the metrics were implemented based on the version of the metrics defined by CESSDA, and evaluated against a collection of reference repositories provided by CESSDA. The requirements and specific standards specified by disciplines such as CESSDA lead to different and distinct metric tests which should facilitate unambiguous automatic FAIR assessment testing.

A set of 33 software repositories were provided by CESSDA for assessment of research software they contained in the social science disciplinary context using the F-UJI tool with the two implemented metrics from milestone M5.6 (section “5 Evaluation of tests in a disciplinary context”). Like with discipline-specific FAIR data assessment results, the CESSDA FAIR research software assessments gave interesting results which may require further investigation, for example, the number of repositories that passed the “dependencies, build and configuration” tests increased with a higher compliance level than with the more basic level compliance. This may have been due to vagueness in the tests at a lower compliance level, or the discipline-specific implementation might be too strict, disregarding other options for complying with the test. The results for the second metric tested (licensing information) were mostly as predicted, however, one of the repositories did not match the expected software stack, so any checks for licence headers in the build script would not be recognised by F-UJI. Further investigation would be needed to add support for other such checks, as well as a discussion whether they should be recognised as in line with the CESSDA guidelines.

¹⁰ Chue Hong, N. P., Katz, D. S., Barker, M., Lamprecht, A.-L., Martinez, C., Psomopoulos, F. E., Harrow, J., Castro, L. J., Gruenpeter, M., Martinez, P. A., Honeyman, T., Struck, A., Lee, A., Loewe, A., van Werkhoven, B., Jones, C., Garijo, D., Plomp, E., Genova, F., ... RDA FAIR4RS WG. (2022). FAIR Principles for Research Software (FAIR4RS Principles) (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00068>

¹¹ FAIR Research Software Metric 13 as proposed by Chue Hong et al., 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10047401>

¹² FAIR Research Software Metric 15 as proposed by Chue Hong et al., 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10047401>

5.1 *Role of the milestone*

The primary role of milestones M5.4 and M5.6 was to implement practical tests for automated FAIR assessment in a disciplinary context for both data objects and research software objects in repositories. However, to test the implementations pilot assessments were run and discussed in those milestones. Thus, this milestone identifies all the discipline-specific pilot assessments for data object and research software (code) objects presented in the previous milestones. Having run the pilot assessments and reviewed the results it has become clear that further investigation is required and the plans for the next steps are described here.

5.1.1 *Means of verification*

Since the first test set of data objects was proposed in milestone M5.1¹³ KNAW-DANS has created a broader set of data objects which cover different situations. In the KNAW-DANS test set the datasets could be either classified as humanities or social sciences but were still of research value to the social science research community of DANS Data Station¹⁴ users. Datasets may have rich, medium or low levels of associated metadata, may, or may not, have a social science specific metadata such as DDI and may have additional metadata. Additionally, access may be open, restricted or metadata only. An important distinction is whether the data are quantitative, having statistical files, or qualitative, for example audio interviews. With a range of dates from 1900 to 2023 the thirty data objects should aid in testing the metric tests for the social sciences. With such a broad collection of data objects we would expect quite different results from a F-UJI test using the social science specific metrics between the different types of data objects. However we discovered with initial tests using F-UJI with the social science specific metrics there was little variation in the results. Therefore, an investigation with the social science specific metrics integrated with the rest of the generic tests and metrics is required to determine if the social science metrics and tests accurately represent the needs of CESSDA as a community, the individual service provider and their designated social science research communities. Moreover, a comparison between assessing the FAIRness using F-UJI of the registry metadata records in the CESSDA Data Catalogue¹⁵ versus the FAIRness assessment of Service Provider repository holdings will evaluate how F-UJI views registries. Additionally running F-UJI tests using generic metrics as well as social science specific metrics will provide the opportunity to evaluate if discipline specificity has any specific benefits for the provider and the user communities.

The development and implementation of discipline-specific metrics and their tests is still evolving. A second pilot will take place in the first quarter of the third year of FAIR-IMPACT, using the KNAW-DANS set of data objects, a broader collection of data objects from UESSEX-UKDS and any equivalent metadata records in the CESSDA Data Catalogue. This will be used to closely analyse if the metric is testing the correct feature of the data objects, if there are issues with the metadata associated with the data object, or if there are problems

¹³ Robert Huber, & Maaïke Verburg. (2023). M5.1 - Reference collection of test data sets (v1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7746205>

¹⁴ <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/social-sciences-and-humanities/>

¹⁵ <https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu>

with the repository management software, and finally if there is benefit in discipline-specific metrics at the level of a discipline as broad as the social sciences.

A difficulty with both the discipline-agnostic metric tests and the CESSDA specific research software FAIR assessment metric tests is that the precision is often unclear. Should the content be checked rigorously, or should a test simply pass when keywords are found? Technical details, for example the keywords, plugins or code snippets, could be valuable to specify when formulating tests for a disciplinary context. Ensuring that all possible variations for metric tests are evaluated complicates the automatic assessment implementation and would obfuscate which actions the developers should take to improve the FAIRness of their software. If a metric test discovers an inaccessible web page perhaps the result should be “not run” instead of “fail” or “pass”, if the metric test definition does not clearly state whether the test should find an accessible web page.

Since milestone M5.6 was published further discipline-agnostic but research software specific metric tests have been developed and implemented in F-UJI thus facilitating a more complete FAIR assessment of research software objects. These and the original metric tests are now being evaluated through a funded FAIR-IMPACT support action: “Assessing and improving Research Software focuses on the assessment and improvement of existing research software using a new extension of F-UJI” (starting 05/2024). The pilot assessments in milestone M5.6 will contribute to the support action and the beta-testing undertaken by the participants. Conversely, the support action will hopefully provide valuable input for issues highlighted here and in milestone 5.6 for research software FAIR assessment in a disciplinary context.

The present report is delivered as a means of verification for this milestone.

6 Conclusions and next steps

Pilot studies for the FAIR assessment of both discipline-specific data and research software (code) was undertaken as part of the integration of these metrics into the F-UJI tool and were reported in the relevant milestones associated with those developments (milestones M5.4 and M5.6).

Evaluation of those results warrants further investigation into how discipline-specific FAIR results can be practically improved using the above mentioned emerging methods, therefore work will continue to evaluate and finetune the metrics specification for use, using the set of data objects which should provide predictable FAIR assessment results. This new set, along with the integration of the social science specific metrics and discipline-agnostic metric tests in F-UJI, should facilitate a detailed overview on the effectiveness of the discipline-specific metrics defined in D5.1 from a CESSDA service provider perspective. We hope to engage with other CESSDA SPs to stimulate further discussions and to garner their perspective on the effectiveness of the social science specific metrics for their holdings, in order to refine and revise our approach if necessary. This activity will be further intensified within task 5.4 when it comes to provide guidelines and specifications to transparently expose such information for portals, repositories and registries.

The evaluation of the research software FAIR metrics in F-UJI as part of the support action will provide valuable insight for discipline-agnostic tests. FAIR research software may become an digital object type which, by its nature, requires discipline-specific tests and metrics. The new structure of F-UJI v3.0 which facilitates user and community developed metric tests will provide a platform for many community defined automated FAIR assessment options. We hope to reevaluate and expand the metrics for research software in the social sciences but this is both dependent upon the results of the support action and the capacity to do so in the final year of FAIR-IMPACT.

The outcomes of this future work, building upon the initial pilots, will be part of a future harmonisation of metrics and tools report.